

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ESSENCE AND CONTENT OF YOUTH INNOVATIVE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Tleuberdinova A.T.

*Scientific Supervisor, Doctor of Economic Sciences,
Professor Institute of Economics of the Ministry of
Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan,
Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Shokhamanova A.M.

*3rd Year PhD Candidates
Karaganda University of Kazpotrebooyuz
Karaganda, Republic of Kazakhstan*

Abstract

The article delineates the essence and content of youth innovative entrepreneurship. The methodological foundation of the research and analysis was based on scholarly works concerning youth issues and innovations in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as statistical analyses. Definitions of entrepreneurship, youth entrepreneurship, and innovative entrepreneurship provided by foreign, Russian, and domestic authors were systematically reviewed and synthesized using grouping and generalization methods. As a result, a definition for the term "youth innovative entrepreneurship" was proposed, and its content was clarified.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, youth entrepreneurship, innovative entrepreneurship, youth innovative entrepreneurship.

The significance of studying youth innovative entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan is linked to its potential impact on the country's economic growth, technological renewal, social changes, international integration, and contributions to education and development. Young entrepreneurs, by developing new

ideas and technologies, contribute to job creation and reduce unemployment levels among youth. The current unemployment rates among youth for the years 2017 – 2023, segmented by regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Unemployment Rates among Youth (ages 15-34) for the Years 2017 – 2023

1	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Republic of Kazakhstan	3,9	3,8	3,7	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,5
Abai	-	-	-	-	-	2,9	2,7
Akmola	3,0	2,9	3,0	3,2	3,1	3,0	3,3
Aktobe	2,9	2,9	3,2	2,9	2,8	2,8	2,5
Almaty	3,0	2,9	3,0	3,4	3,4	3,3	3,1
Atyrau	2,2	2,4	2,4	2,4	2,4	2,4	2,6
West Kazakhstan	3,9	3,8	3,8	3,9	3,9	4,0	3,8
Zhambyl	2,5	2,9	2,8	2,9	2,8	3,0	3,1
Zhetysu	-	-	-	-	-	4,2	3,8
Karaganda	4,9	4,9	4,8	5,0	4,7	4,5	3,0
Kostanay	3,0	3,1	3,3	3,2	3,0	2,8	3,1
Kyzylorda	4,3	4,2	4,2	4,3	4,1	4,0	3,5
Mangystau	3,7	2,9	3,1	3,6	3,7	3,4	4,1
South Kazakhstan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pavlodar	3,3	3,6	3,0	3,0	2,8	2,7	2,6
North Kazakhstan	2,7	3,0	3,0	3,9	2,9	3,6	4,8
Turkestan	4,3	3,2	3,2	3,4	3,6	3,9	2,8
Ulytau	-	-	-	-	-	4,3	3,7
East Kazakhstan	3,9	3,8	3,4	3,2	3,0	3,9	3,4
Astana City	4,5	4,5	4,5	4,6	4,6	4,6	4,0
Almaty City	6,7	6,4	6,1	5,9	5,8	5,5	5,2
Shymkent City	3,8	4,2	3,9	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,7

Note: The table is compiled based on information from the National Statistics Bureau of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Given the statistical data, from 2017 to 2023, the unemployment rate among youth in Kazakhstan remained approximately stable, although there was a slight decrease of 0.3% in 2023. This is a minimal change; however, our goal is to reduce the unemployment rate among youth, primarily through the development of youth innovative entrepreneurship. Additionally, fostering youth innovative entrepreneurship contributes to the national economy's growth. The technological aptitude and innovativeness of youth enhance the country's competitiveness in the global market. Through entrepreneurial activities, youth address societal issues and strive for social improvements. Moreover, these activities open pathways to the global market, strengthening Kazakhstan's role on the international stage. Active engagement in this sector not only enhances their knowledge and skills but also opens avenues for professional development. The necessity to develop and support this entrepreneurial spirit among Kazakhstan's youth is evident, playing a crucial role in ensuring long-term economic and social stability.

The theoretical foundations of developing youth innovative entrepreneurship are linked to

entrepreneurship theories, principles of innovative entrepreneurship, and how this phenomenon influences the economic and social development of youth. Entrepreneurship theories explore the central role of the entrepreneur, the processes of recognizing and exploiting entrepreneurial opportunities. Joseph Schumpeter and his theory of "creative destruction" propose ideas about restructuring and advancing the market through innovations. According to Schumpeter's model, innovative entrepreneurship generates economic growth by creating new technologies, products, services, and markets. Innovative entrepreneurship is based on novelty, a readiness for risk, and creativity. This process is oriented towards commercializing new ideas, achieving market dominance, and instigating social changes. Significant aspects influencing youth entrepreneurship include digital technologies, the network economy, and startup culture. To elucidate the concept of "youth entrepreneurship," the works of several authors were reviewed, with their definitions analyzed and displayed in Table 2. This table includes definitions from foreign, Russian, and domestic scholars.

Table 2.

Theoretical Overview of the Definitions of 'Youth Entrepreneurship'

№	Author	Definition
1	Chigunta, 2002, p. 2	The practical application of enterprising qualities such as initiative, innovation, creativity, and risk taking into the work environment (either in self-employment or employment in small start-up firms), using the appropriate skills necessary for success in that environment and culture [1].
2	Schoof, 2006	Entrepreneurship is the recognition of an opportunity to create value, and the process of acting on this opportunity, whether or not it involves the formation of a new entity. While concepts such as "innovation" and "risk taking" in particular are usually associated with entrepreneurship, they are not necessary to define the term [2]
3	Emmanuel Kojo Oseifuah	... youth entrepreneurs are defined as young people from 15 to 35 years old who recognise an opportunity to create value or wealth in an existing or new enterprise, irrespective of the sector [3].
4	Sonia Riahi	Youth entrepreneurship benefits an economy by creating jobs, increasing competitiveness, creating innovative goods and services, creating a strong community and cultural identity, and producing income [4].
5	Mezentseva E.V..	... the author defines youth entrepreneurship as including individuals aged 14 to 30 who engage in entrepreneurial activities in the form of individual, collective, or corporate entrepreneurship, demonstrating initiative and acting at their own risk with the aim of earning entrepreneurial income to satisfy social, cultural, material needs, and ensuring a decent standard of living for their families [5].
6	Akhiiarova, N.V.	... youth entrepreneurship is defined as the independent business activity of enterprising young people, which is lawful and based on certain resources, autonomous socio-economic initiative, innovativeness, personal qualities, and responsibility. It aims not only to generate profit and achieve material well-being but also to allow for the free self-realization and self-affirmation of the individual [6].
7	Shiliaeva, A.S.	... youth entrepreneurship can be characterized as normatively defined and informal social relations that arise from the active and initiative activities of youth (ages 14 – 35), as economic entities (individual or collective) in the fields of production, exchange, distribution, and consumption of material and spiritual goods. It depends on the specifics of social systems, the level of market relations development, and the personal qualities of the entrepreneur (age, accumulated knowledge and experience, value orientations, ability to take risks and be responsible for the outcomes of their activities) [7].
8	Khusainova, Zh.S., Zhartai, Zh.M.	... Youth entrepreneurship is a distinct independent segment of small and medium-sized enterprises, represented by entrepreneurs up to 30 years old, who engage in initiative-driven entrepreneurial activities in various organizational and legal forms and effectively combine production factors based on their specific personal qualities (flexibility, mobility, energy, innovative activity, predisposition to risk) to meet existing or newly created societal needs with the aim of generating entrepreneurial income [8].

Analyzing the above definitions, it has been determined that youth entrepreneurship is associated with initiative, innovation, and generating profit through the creation of new products. Youth innovative entrepreneurship helps address employment issues, achieve sustainable growth, and enhance social inclusiveness. For example, startups led by young people have a positive socio-economic impact by attracting investment to the local economy and creating new jobs.

Key factors influencing the development of youth entrepreneurship include entrepreneurship-oriented programs within the education system, support infrastructure (such as incubators and accelerators), availability of financial resources, and the legislative environment. Challenges include underdeveloped entrepreneurial culture, bureaucracy, and high tax rates. By adequately addressing these issues and considering youth innovative entrepreneurship as a distinct sector, we can contribute to the advancement of our economy.

Youth innovative entrepreneurship is a driver for economic development, enriching the state budget through the growth of small and medium enterprises, and implementing innovative ideas.

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